

USE OF DIDACTIC MATERIALS IN MOTHER TONGUE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article covers the use of didactic materials in mother tongue classes. In particular, today in our country, great attention is being paid to the educational process, the education of students and the motivation of teachers who teach them. This places great responsibility on teachers. This article is dedicated to the importance of using didactic games in the effective organization of mother tongue lessons.

Key words: didactic games, "Word to word" game, lexicology, common nouns, similar nouns, object, composition, didactic games, education.

Introduction: The educational process, its development and effective passage largely depend on the open communication between the teacher and the students based on mutual trust. Games in the course of the lesson play a key role in strengthening this environment. The games get used to working in groups and don't take much time. During team work, students become more active and pay more attention to the lesson.

Analysis of the result: By means of games, giving students new knowledge, building skills, and stimulating the creative abilities of small group members. It is advisable to conduct games mainly in the introductory or final part of the lesson. Games can be divided into 7 types according to their purpose. "Find a word from a word" game. In this game, you are required to make several words from one word. This type of game encourages students to think, search, and develops their resourcefulness. We don't want to repeat this game exactly, but we want to think about ways to play it depending on a certain theme. Several words can be formed using different combinations of letters in a given word. So, this game can be played in connection with a certain topic. Word-to-word game can be used to teach all levels of language. In particular, this game can be used to study the topics of similar and opposite meaning words in the lexicology department. For this, the teacher should be able to choose words that can create similar or opposite meanings and then bring them to the attention of the students. After studying the topic of homonyms, the students are given the task of giving the following words and generating similar words from them. Independently, with participation, in the shallows. From the independent word do (verb to do, to do hair), language (verb to want, the name of a body part), from the participle word tor (a musical instrument, a word characteristic of the adjective group), kir (the verb to enter, a word belonging to the adjective group), noun (noun, animal name, verb to shoot), osh (name of food, verb to eat) are derived. This game can be partially used on the topic of antonyms. After working out exercises on the subject and giving the necessary concepts, students are given the words pine trees, eye, bead and are instructed to come up with antonyms. It is possible to form the words black and white from the word pine trees, and the words alkok from the words eye and bead. This game can also be widely used in the morphology department. The task is to create proper nouns from

the given words in the noun group. Nouns can be formed from the word "to scholars" as follows: 1. Nouns with nouns. Nadir, Rim, Ali, Dilbar, Lola, Nil, Narimon. 2. Similar nouns. a) kinship nouns: brother, mother, child; b) product names: grain, lemon, in, building, ball; c) abstract nouns: medicine, knowledge, faith. The game can be played in the same way in the rest of the word groups. There is also an opportunity to use the game to strengthen knowledge specific to the syntax section. Only in this section it is conducted in the style of "Word to sentence". In the 5th grade, this game can be used when studying the topics "Simple compound sentence" and "Simple compound sentence". For this, the students are given a word to our experts and they turn the word into a simple sentence. Pupils will be able to make all kinds of simple and common sentences: The flower opened, the boy went, the pupils looked for Lola, etc. All in all, Word-to-Word is a great game that kids love, and it's no exaggeration to say that the extent to which it can be used depends on the skill of the teacher.

"Find a word from a word" game. This game teaches students to be sensitive, intelligent and resourceful. In order to participate in the game, if the children have mastered the lesson well, the result will be high, if they have not mastered it well, they will be left out of the game. Therefore, if the student always prepares well for the lesson, he will always succeed not only in learning in such games. Such games can be used continuously to learn all levels of the language. In particular, it is appropriate to use this game by repeating the lessons held on the topic of synonyms in the lexicology department. The game is played in the following order: their sequence is as follows. The teacher chooses several groups of words with the same meaning. For example, face, bet, aft, bashara, face; sun, day, sun, bowl, before, before, nose; deliberately, hand, wall, special. These words are written on separate pieces of paper and placed on the table. From these, the main words are separated and given to 4 students. So, four students stand in four places holding a piece of paper with the main word written on it. The remaining words are mixed up. The students of the class are also divided into four groups and each group is assigned one head word. For example, the students of the 1st group are assigned to find synonyms of the word face, the 2nd group of the word first, the 3rd group of the word sun, and the 4th group of the word deliberately. The students of group 1 go out in turn, find the words bet, aft, bashara, chehra from among the words in the mixed state, next to the student who holds the paper with the word face, i.e. "Head word" They take place next to z». The remaining members of the group continue the game in this way, that is, they find their place. The teacher checks the resourcefulness of the groups, how they did it, the groups that found their places correctly are given full marks, and the groups that are wrong in finding their places are given lower marks. It is also possible to make the game a little more complicated. For this purpose, if words that do not belong to the same meaning line are mixed into the words with the same meaning, it becomes difficult for the students to find the necessary word. This work is determined according to the knowledge and talent of students. This game is played in the same order on the topic of nested words, similar words, phrases. The use of this game is effective in studying the topics of semantic groups of verbs, verb ratios, basic and artificial verbs, semantic groups of adjectives, and semantic groups of pronouns in the morphology department.

Conclusion: Didactic games are very useful games for perfect understanding of each lesson. Didactic games help children to develop their thinking and movement, as a result of which unity is born in children's perception (sight, hearing, skin sense organ signs). This affects the students to think about what the teacher said and understand it mentally, that is, it

encourages them to follow the rules of the didactic game themselves. The structure of didactic games in this way makes it possible to analyze the activity of students. That's why all children act with great interest during the game. "White poplar, blue poplar" game. This game is one of the games that children love to play, and it can also be used in the educational process. This game teaches children to think quickly and be resourceful. Objects In games with toys and real objects, children learn to play with them and compare them, learn similarities and differences between objects. they know about: color, size, shape, quality: children understand any game, and through these games, the child's thinking develops. The word game objects are fully described. The didactic task is that they should be prepared for this game. To choose a didactic game, it is necessary to know the existing knowledge and ideas of the games, because it is necessary to work with the existing knowledge and ideas in the games. For the game "Find the pair" you will need: cut the sheet into cardboard. When a set of 10 pairs of cards is formed, before starting the game, shuffle the cards and pick them face up, face up, if the players match the cards, that is, if the words and pictures match. Isa takes the third card from him and continues to draw the next pair of cards.

If the cards do not match, the player puts them in their previous position, i.e. upside down, and the turn to open from the cards goes to the next player. The player who collects the most cards wins. Such games develop children's thinking and increase their interest in learning.

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